

SIMULATION AND ANALYSIS OF PROCESS-INDUCED DISTORTIONS FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

LIU Kai^{*1}, ZHANG Boming¹, YE Jinrui¹, Tang zhanwen¹, Jiang tian¹

¹ School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing 100191, China
Email: liukai96200@yeah.net, web page: <http://www.buaa.edu.cn>

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ABSTRACT

Process-induced distortions (PID) of fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composites bring many problems to parts assembly. A multi-level simulation method for cure process of composite integrated structure was developed to simplify calculation and improve accuracy of prediction. Panels and stiffened panels were manufactured by autoclave process to verify the simulation method. It is found that numerical predictions compared quite well with experimental measurements. Furthermore, PID investigations were carried out for thermoplastic composites produced by thermoforming process. Both process features and material characters were incorporated in simulation. Concerning hemispheres with symmetric lay-ups, stamping induced stresses play a dominant role in PID and determine the deformation trend; fiber reorientations have an important effect on the thermally induced deformations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials have been widely used in aircraft, automobile and sporting goods.^[1] Integrated process is an important technique for composites to reduce parts and fasteners and meet the needs of structure performance. Cure-induced deformation is a key problem to improve process quality of large-scale and complex integrated structure made of composite materials. For reducing cure-induced deformation, conventional method is to adjust and correct the skin of mold and cure system again and again according as experiences and process tests. But this kind of trial and error method increases fabrication cost. So it is important to develop a simulation method of predicting cure-induced deformation for composite structures, to guarantee product quality and reduce fabrication cost.^[2]

Investigations have been developed into cure-induced deformation and residual stress distribution for composites. Yi^[3] et al. developed a nonlinear finite element model to analyze the residual stresses in thermoset composites during cool-down after curing. Lee and Sohn^[4] added the residual stresses in the curing period to the thermal stresses in the cool-down period to make up the total residual stress. Yoon and Kim^[5] researched the effect of thermal deformation and chemical shrinkage on the process-induced distortion of carbon/epoxy curved laminates. Nuri Ersoy and Kevin Potter^[6] considered that composite parts manufactured by autoclave processes had manufacturing distortions due to unavoidable physical mechanisms that took place during the process. Kim and Daniel^[7] applied a more direct method to measure the strain in the cure process. They used fiber Bragg grating and resistance strain chip buried inside the composite materials to measure the changing of the strain. It was found that the reciprocity between mold and part leads to evident strain in the cure process. Satish^[8] applied shear layer to replace the influence of mold on the composite material by simulation. The method can accurately predict the curing deformation generated by the reciprocity between mold and part.

In this study, a multi-level simulation method for cure process of composite structures was developed. Several simplified models were involved in multi-level simulation method, including equivalent temperature load model and shear layer model. Thermal deformation, cure shrinkage and

*Corresponding author: LIU Kai. Tel.: +86 010 82338756; E-mail address: liukai96200@yeah.net.

mold effect were considered in analysis. Panels, panels and sandwich structures were made to verify the simulation method. Furthermore, PID investigations were carried out for thermoplastic composites produced by thermoforming process. Both process features and material characters were incorporated in simulation.

2 MULTI-LEVEL SIMULATION METHOD

Figure 1: Multi-level simulation method to predict cure-induced deformation

In multi-level simulation method, cure-induced deformation of different kinds of composite structures was investigated in order of structure complexity. Cure-induced deformation of complex structures was predicted based on solutions obtained from studies of simple composite structures. Additional factors were taken into model to adapt to structural characteristic when the studied composite structure became more complex. Totally, three factors were taken into consideration, including thermal shrinkage, cure shrinkage and mold effect. But the deformation induced by these three factors had different ratio with respect to different kinds of structures. The objective of multi-level simulation method is to predict cure-induced deformation of real complex composite structures, so the model used must be as simplified as possible. Therefore, subordinate effect factors could be neglected to reach a balance between predicting accuracy and time cost. And some semi-empirical models are suitable to be selected.

a) Equivalent temperature load model

In autoclave processing, the shrinkage of composite material (ε^{total}) consists of two parts: cure shrinkage (denoted as ε^h) aroused by cure reaction of resin and thermal shrinkage (denoted as ε^r) taking place in cooling stage after resin was cured completely, as described in equation (1).^[9]

$$\varepsilon^{total} = \varepsilon^h + \varepsilon^r \quad (1)$$

ε^r depends on the thermal expansion coefficient of composites. ε^h is related to the complex cure reaction of resin and is difficult to simulate. A semi-empirical model was proposed to regard ε^h as an equivalent temperature load. In equivalent temperature load model, complex cure reaction is not taken into consideration and a lot of iterative computations were avoided.

$$\varepsilon^r = \alpha \Delta T^r \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon^h = \alpha \Delta T^h \quad (3)$$

then

$$\varepsilon^{total} = \alpha (\Delta T^r + \Delta T^h) \quad (4)$$

where α represents the thermal expansion coefficient of composites that have cured completely. ΔT^r represents the difference between cure temperature and room temperature. ΔT^h represented the equivalent temperature difference.

As

$$\varepsilon^h / \varepsilon^r = \Delta T^h / \Delta T^r \quad (5)$$

then

$$\Delta T^h = \Delta T^r \cdot \varepsilon^h / \varepsilon^r \quad (6)$$

$\varepsilon^h / \varepsilon^r$ could be obtained from fiber Bragg grating experiments. Finally, the equivalent temperature difference was determined according to equation (6).

Figure 2: Bragg grating experiment results

b) Shear layer model

There is a large body of evidence confirming the occurrence of tool-part interaction. The thermal expansion coefficient difference between composites and mold will contribute to cure-induced deformation. A shear layer was added to the surface of composites in touch with mould. The shear layer is part of the composites and acts in the temperature rising period after the gelling point of composites. Because of the shear layer, there was a stress gradient in the thickness direction of composites. Shear layer has two parameters: thickness (t_s) and thermal expansion coefficient (α_s). Shear layer parameters (t_s and α_s) were determined from unidirectional laminate experiments ($[0]_3$, $[0]_4$, $[0]_5$, $[0]_6$).

Figure 3: unidirectional laminate experiments

Figure 4: t_s and α_s determination

3 SIMULATION VERIFICATION

3.2 Laminates by autoclave process

Figure 5: Asymmetric panels

Label	Stack sequence	Experimental maximum warpage /mm	Simulation /mm	Error /%
1	[45/90 ₂ /-45 ₂ /0 ₂ /45]	3	2.8	6.67
2	[0 ₃ /45 ₄]	12.5	11.6	7.20
3	[0/0/45/45]	13.5	16.4	21.48
4	[0/0/45/0]	13.5	10.7	20.74
5	[0/90/-45 ₂ /90/0/45 ₂]	14	12.3	12.14
6	[0/0/45/-45]	15.5	15.5	0.00
7	[90/90/45/45]	17.5	13.8	21.14
8	[90/45/45/0]	18.5	16.5	10.81
9	[90/90/90/45]	27.5	23.3	15.27
10	[90/90/45/-45]	30.5	28.0	8.20

Table 1: Simulation and experimental results of asymmetric panels

Ten laminates with asymmetric stack sequence were manufactured to verify the multi-level simulation method. Laminate geometry was 150*75 mm. Simulation and experimental results are shown in Table 1. Value of cure induced deformation lied between 2 to 30 mm. Predicting accuracy of multi-level simulation method was 85% more or less.

3.3 Stiffened panels by autoclave process

Figure 6: geometry of stiffened panels.

Figure 7: Simulation and actual deformation of stiffened panels under co-cure

Figure 8: Simulation and actual deformation of stiffened panels under co-bonding with cured stringer and uncured skin

Figure 9: Simulation and actual deformation of stiffened panels under co-bonding with cured skin and uncured stringer

Process	The maximal displacement of skin		Error%
	Experimental	Simulation	
Co-cure	39.2	36.1	8.01
Co-bonding(cured stringer)	34.4	31.4	8.72
Co-bonding(cured skin)	35.9	32.3	10.0

Table 2: The maximal displacement of skin at different curing scheme

Simulation and experimental results of stiffened panels are displayed in Figure. 9-11 and Table. 3. Deformation trend predicted by multi-level model is consistent with experimental results. Prediction accuracy is more than 80%. With regard to stiffened panels, a special problem is curing scheme. Different curing schemes lead to deformation variation, but this kind of difference is limited. A stress transfer model was utilized to describe the effect of curing scheme on deformation.^[10] Due to limited space, the stress transfer model is not introduced here.

3.3 thermoplastic composite hemispheres by thermoforming process

Both process features and material characteristics should be embedded in PID calculation. In the past decades, most studies on the PID subject were carried out for thermosetting composites manufactured by autoclave process, RTM, hot press etc. Researches on thermoplastic composites are scarcely available, especially those on thermoplastic composite structures produced by thermoforming. Different from traditional processes, the 2D blank in thermoforming is stamped into a 3D shape by external forces. Fiber reorientations may take place if doubly-curved structures are encountered and

stamping induced stresses are preserved in the structures. Thus, a priori, those features may have an influence on the PID of composites.

Uniaxial prepreg, approximately 0.25 mm thick, composed of a poly-propylene (PP) homopolymer matrix containing 60% volume fraction E-glass fibers, has been used. The thermoforming set-up is shown in Fig. 10 (a). Before thermoforming, the prepreg was cut into 240*240 mm squares and stacked into a blank, which was attached to the blank-holder frame by springs using clips. The stacking consequence of the blank was [0/90/0/90]s.

Figure 10 Fig. 1 (a) thermoforming set-up; (b) hemispherical mold; (c) blank-holder

An example of a thermoformed part is shown in Fig. 11(a). Because of the anisotropy of the composite material and the effect of the springs, the part takes on a petal shape. It was finally trimmed into a hemisphere, as shown in Fig. 11(b). Obvious process-induced distortions are observed. The cross-section profile of the hemisphere is not the same as the mold shape. It is an ellipse rather than a circle, with a major axis 124.5mm ($U=0.25$ mm) in the 0° direction and a minor axis 123 mm ($U=-0.5$ mm) in the 90° direction. PID is denoted as U , which is calculated from the axis (L). Outward deformation occurs when U is positive and inward distortion is represented by negative U .

$$U = (L - 124\text{mm}) / 2 \tag{7}$$

Figure 11 (a) a thermoformed part; (b) a finally trimmed hemisphere; (c) the coordinate to describe deformations; (d) fiber orientations in 45° direction; (e) shear angle measurement; (f) fiber orientations in 0° direction.

Figure 12 (a) predicted distortions of a thermoformed part before trimming; (b) simulation results of PID of a hemisphere; (c) the predicted PID neglecting stamping residual stresses; (d) the predicted PID neglecting both stamping residual stresses and fiber reorientations. (Deformation scale factor 10)

It is shown in Fig. 11 that obvious fiber reorientations occur after thermoforming. In the direction of 0° and 90° , the shear angle is approximately equal to zero, showing that no shear deformation takes place in these regions; in the directions of $\pm 45^\circ$, the absolute values of shear angles reach their maximums, shear deformation takes place in bursts in these regions.

To evaluate the effect of FR quantitatively, the total process induced distortions (PID) are divided into thermally induced deformation (TID) and stamping induced deformation. Fig. 12 (c) demonstrates the thermally induced distortions of hemispheres. Obvious TID is observed and varies with different directions. However, uniform shrinkage manifests and TID is in a negligibly small amount when fiber reorientations are neglected, as demonstrated in Fig. 12(d). This is because both the stiffness properties and the expansion behaviors of the hemisphere change locally as a function of the fiber reorientation. An inhomogeneous distribution of these properties leads to non-uniform shrinkage and hence to further product distortions. This non-uniform shrinkage plays a crucial role for TID of symmetric lay-up hemispheres.

It is proved in Figure 12(b) and Figure 11(b) that the simulation method could accurately predict shape distortions of hemispheres. In the 0° direction, the contour of the hemisphere expands outward. However, the contour of the hemisphere springs inward if the stamping residual stresses are ignored. Therefore, stamping induced stresses play a dominant role in PID for hemispheres with symmetric lay-ups and determine the deformation trend.

4 CONCLUSION

A multi-level simulation method for cure process of composite integrated structure was developed to simplify calculation and improve accuracy of prediction. Equivalent temperature load model and shear layer model were introduced. A mass of experiments were carried out to verify the multi-level simulation method, including panels, L-shape beams, stiffened panels and sandwich structures. Results show that the adopted simulation method can be used to predict the cure-induced deformation for different kinds of structures, with accuracy of 80%.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. J. Morgan, E. E. Shin, J. Lincoln, et al, Overview of polymer matrix composites performance and materials development for aerospace applications, *SAMPE Journal*, **37**, 2001, pp.102-107.
- [2] Yue Guangquan, Study on simulation and control method of cure-induced deformation for integrated composite panel [D], Harbin, Harbin Institute of Technology, 2010.
- [3] S. Yi, K. S. Chian and H. H. Hilton, Nonlinear viscoelastic finite element analyses of thermosetting polymeric composites during cool-down after curing, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **36**, 2002, pp.3-17.
- [4] S. S. Lee and Y. S. Sohn, Viscoelastic analysis of residual stresses in a unidirectional laminate, *Structural Engineering and Mechanics*, **4**, 1994, pp.383-393.
- [5] K. J. Yoon and J. S. Kim, Effect of thermal deformation and chemical shrinkage on the process induced distortion of carbon/epoxy curved laminates, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **35**, 2001, pp. 253-263.
- [6] N. Ersoy, K. Potter, M. R. Wisnom, An experimental method to study the frictional processes during composites manufacturing, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **36**, 2005, pp.1536-1544.
- [7] Kim, Daniel, Cure cycle effect on composite structures manufactured by resin transfer molding, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **36**, 2002, pp.1725-1743.
- [8] K. B. Satish and V. S. Lloyd, A linear finite element model to predict processing-induced distortion in FRP laminates, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **36**, 2005, pp.1666-1674.
- [9] Tang zhanwen, Zhang boming, Prediction of curing deformation in integrated design and manufacture of composites, *Aeronautical Manufacturing Technology*, **15**, 2014, pp.32-37.
- [10] Jiang tian, Zhangboming, Simulation and verification of cure-induced deformation by stages for integrated composite structure, *Acta Materiae Compositae Sinica*, **30**, 2013, pp.61-66.